

Open Repositories 2026

Online | 8 - 11 June 2026

Conference Agenda

MON 08 June	TUE 09 June	WED 10 June	THU 11 June
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Agenda Overview

Date: Monday, 08/June/2026

11:30 - 18:00

[Online Express](#)

Location: [Online Express](#)

Recordings available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/openrepos/records?q=lightning%20AND%20talk&f=subject%3AOR2026>

4TU.ResearchData; a community-driven approach for building an open, domain-specific repository for data and software

[Madelaine de Smaele](#), [Daniel Bangert](#), [Gabriela Kuhn](#)

4TU.ResearchData / TU Delft Library, Netherlands, The

A data storage crisis: how UC Berkeley utilized Dataverse to Respond to faculty data needs

[Anna Sackmann](#), [maria matienzo](#)

University of California Berkeley, United States of America

A Little UX Goes a Long Way: How You Can Do Lightweight Testing to Identify Priorities

[Sara Byrd](#)

NSF National Center for Atmospheric Research, United States of America

Adding Institutional Equipment and Facilities to the Research Activity Snapshot in DSpace-CRIS

[Pablo De Castro](#)^{1,2}, [Susanna Mornati](#)³, [Oliver Goldschmidt](#)⁴

1: euroCRIS, The Netherlands; 2: University of Strathclyde Glasgow, United Kingdom; 3: 4Science S.p.A, Italy; 4: Technical University of Hamburg (TUHH), Germany

Archiving under duress: methodologies and tools

[Stefano Cossu](#)

N/A, United States of America

Ask a robot - adding AI search to InvenioRDM

[Steven Eardley](#)

Cottage Labs, United Kingdom

Balancing Openness, Usability, and Community in Public Health Data

[Hannah Olson-Williams](#)

University of Wisconsin-Madison, United States of America

Data Modelling in EPrints 3v5

[Justin Bradley](#), [David Newman](#), [Edward Oakley](#), [William Robertson](#), [Luke Wallin](#), [Richard Cook](#)

EPrints Services, United Kingdom

Demonstrating the value of capturing conference posters in amber – the home of ambulance service research.

[Matt Holland](#)¹, [Michelle Dutton](#)², [Steve Glover](#)²

1: Library and Knowledge Service for NHS Ambulance Services in England (LKS ASE); 2: Manchester University NHS Foundation Trust Library Service

Designing an external metadata harvester for DSpace: Lessons from the Imec Repository

[Łukasz Wawer](#), [Mateusz Adamiak](#)

PCG Academia, Poland

Designing Open Repository Agreements for a Generative AI World: Mitigating Risks While Enabling Open Knowledge Exchange

[Agnes Gambill West](#)

Appalachian State University, United States of America

From Storage Groups to Stories: Evolving Collections in FRDR

[Neha Milan](#)

Digital Research Alliance of Canada, Canada

Harnessing CRIS systems to improve disambiguation of sub-organisational units

Miriam Baglioni¹, Stefania Amodeo², Michele Artini¹, Michele De Bonis¹, Paolo Manghi^{1,2}

1: ISTI-CNR; 2: OpenAIRE

Incorporating AI Into Your Repository When You'd Rather Not

Rebekah Kati

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, United States of America

Institutional Repositories in Small Island States - The Open Knowledge Repository of the University of Aruba

Esther Plomp

University of Aruba, Aruba (The Netherlands)

Integrating Quality and Impact Metrics in Digital Repositories: The HERA Module for DSpace.

Juan Cruz Mazullo¹, Gonzalo Lújan Villarreal^{1,2}, Lautaro Josin Saller¹, Ariel Jorge Lira^{1,2}

1: PrEBI-SEDICI Universidad Nacional de La Plata; 2: CESGI, Comisión de Investigaciones Científicas

The Invisible Problem: Marketing and Culture in Data Repositories

Dayane Dornelles^{1,2}, Luciana Mara Silva¹

1: Universidade do Estado de Santa Catarina (Udesc), Brazil; 2: Instituto Brasileiro de Informação em Ciência e Tecnologia (Ibict), Brazil

Open cost data in repositories – FAIR enough?

Lisa-Marie Stein¹, Alexander Wagner¹, Dirk Pieper³, Julia Bartlewska³, Christoph Broschinski³, Gernot Deinzer², Bianca Schweighofer², Colin Sippl², Silke Weisheit², Cornelia Lang², Robert Bosek²

1: DESY, Germany; 2: Universität Regensburg, Germany; 3: Universität Bielefeld, Germany

Open knowledge exchange inside universities: turning repositories into daily workflows, not side projects

Mustafa Kayyali

Maaref University of Applied Sciences, Syrian Arab Republic

Scoring AI for Accessibility: A Rubric-Based Framework

Sarah Cogley, Anne Bouvier, Stacy Snyder, Lisa McLaughlin

State University of New York at Buffalo, United States of America

Strategic Recommendations for Professionalizing the Open Access Repository Infrastructure in Germany

Jonas Höfting, Heinz Pampel, Lisa Matthias, Laura Rothfritz

Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany

Strengthening and growing a creative and practice-led research repository through collaborative approaches

Loretta S. Khanna

Griffith University, Australia

Sustaining Open Educational Resources through Institutional Repositories and Collaborative Networks: A Library–Distance Education Partnership in Argentina

Victor Marcos Ferracutti, Nancy Ambar Ferracutti

Universidad Nacional del Sur, Argentine Republic

Towards the integration of CORE into DSpace

Viktoria Pavlenko¹, Matteo Cancellieri¹, Giuseppe Digilio², Andrea Bollini², Petr Knoth¹

1: The Open University, United Kingdom; 2: 4Science

University of Edinburgh Streamlined Research Data Service Feasibility Study

Robin Rice, Ianthe Sutherland

University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom

What Happens to the Old Site? Archiving West Chester University Digital Commons During a Redesign

Julia Doelling

West Chester University, United States of America

12:00 - 15:00

Workshop: InvenioRDM Workshop

Location: Parallel Session 1

Session Chair A: William J. Nixon, Research Libraries UK (RLUK)

Session Chair B: Ianthe Sutherland, University of Edinburgh

Recording available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778543>

InvenioRDM Workshop

Matthew B. Carson¹, Sara Gonzales¹, Aaron McCollough², Tom Morrell³, Maximilian Moser⁴, Kate Pechekhonova⁵, Nicola Tarocco⁶, Deb Verhoff⁵, Guillaume Viger¹, Esteban Gabanchó², Pearl Go¹, Karen Gutzman¹, Alex Ioannidis⁶, Pal Kerecsenyi⁶, Saksham Arora⁶

1: Northwestern University, Gatter Health Sciences Library & Learning Center, Chicago, IL, USA; 2: Ubiquity Press, London, UK; 3: Caltech, Pasadena, CA, USA; 4: TU Wien, Vienna, Austria; 5: NYU Libraries, New York, NY, USA; 6: European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), Geneva, Switzerland

Workshop: Automated subject indexing with Annif

Location: Parallel Session 2

Session Chair A: Iryna Kuchma, Electronic Information for Libraries (EIFL)

Session Chair B: Lazarus Matizirofa, University of the Witwatersrand

Recording available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20788961>

Automated subject indexing with Annif

Osma Suominen¹, Mona Lehtinen¹, Juho Inkinen¹, Ghulam Mustafa Majal², Argie Kasprzik², Lakshmi Rajendram Bashyam², Christoph Poley³, Maximilian Kähler³

1: National Library of Finland, Finland; 2: ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics, Germany; 3: German National Library, Germany

15:00 - 16:00

Workshop: DSpace Seed – Creating gigantic repositories with a new python library

Location: Parallel Session 2

Session Chair A: Kimberly Chapman, University of Arizona Libraries

Session Chair B: Erin Jerome, University of Massachusetts Amherst

Recording available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20789060>

DSpace Seed – Creating gigantic repositories with a new python library

Bram Luyten

	Atmire, Belgium
15:00 - 17:00	<p>Workshop: OCFL Tutorial: Foundations, Affordances and Implementations Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Paul Walk, Antleaf Ltd. Session Chair B: Kathryn Cassidy, Trinity College Dublin Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20789110</p> <p>OCFL Tutorial: Foundations, Affordances and Implementations Simeon Warner¹, Neil Jefferies², Rosalyn Metz³, Andrew Woods⁴, Julian Morley⁵, Miguel Blanco⁶, Dan Field⁷, Tom Crane⁸ 1: Cornell University, USA; 2: Open Preservation Foundation; 3: Emory University, USA; 4: Harvard University, USA; 5: Stanford University, USA; 6: LIBNOVA; 7: Lyrasis; 8: Digirati</p>
17:00 - 17:50	<p>Round Table: Cross-Community Collaboration: What Could Solidarity Do for Us? Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Kathryn Cassidy, Trinity College Dublin Session Chair B: Torsten Reimer, University of Chicago No recording available. Round Table sessions were not recorded.</p> <p>Cross-Community Collaboration: What Could Solidarity Do for Us? Heather Greer Klein¹, Arran Griffith² 1: Samvera, United States of America; 2: Fedora, United States of America</p>
17:00 - 20:00	<p>Workshop: Introduction to Modern Islandora: Architecture, Metadata, and Discoverability Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Joseph Kraus, Colorado School of Mines Session Chair B: Gustavo Durand, Harvard University Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20789066</p> <p>Introduction to Modern Islandora: Architecture, Metadata, and Discoverability Akanksha Singh¹, Natalie Baur², Joe Corall³, Aubrey Shanahan⁴ 1: Discoverygarden Inc, Canada; 2: University of Iowa; 3: Lehigh University; 4: Islandora</p>
18:00 - 18:50	<p>Round Table: The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly: An Open Discussion of Digital Preservation Approaches and Challenges Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Torsten Reimer, University of Chicago Session Chair B: Emily Bongiovanni, Carnegie Mellon University No recording available. Round Table sessions were not recorded.</p> <p>The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly: An Open Discussion of Digital Preservation Approaches and Challenges Marcella Lees Art Institute of Chicago, United States of America</p>
19:00 - 19:50	<p>Round Table: AI and Repository Takedown Requests: Policies, Practices, and Shared Challenges Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Maureen Walsh, The Ohio State University Session Chair B: Torsten Reimer, University of Chicago No recording available. Round Table sessions were not recorded.</p> <p>AI and Repository Takedown Requests: Policies, Practices, and Shared Challenges Kirsten Markusic, Lisa Chinn University of Chicago</p>

Date: Tuesday, 09/June/2026

12:00 - 13:45	<p>Welcome & Opening Keynote Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Elizabeth Krznarich, University of Wisconsin Session Chair B: Maureen Walsh, The Ohio State University Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20789141</p> <p>Opening Keynote Kathleen Shearer¹, Danny Kingsley², Kazu Yamaji³, Omo Oaiya⁴, Lautaro Matas⁵ 1: Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR); 2: Deakin University; 3: National Institute of Informatics (NII); 4: West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN); 5: LA Referencia</p>	
14:00 - 14:50	<p>Developer Track: DSpace 1 (DSpace 10 and DSpace Merger) Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Maureen Walsh, The Ohio State University Session Chair B: Ianthe Sutherland, University of Edinburgh Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778587</p> <p>DSpace Merger: Authority Framework vs Relationship Framework Vincenzo Mecca, Giuseppe Digilio, Adamo Fapohunda, Francesco Molinaro 4Science, Italy</p> <p>Enhancing Transparency in Repositories: Exploring the DSpace 10 Audit Trail Feature Stefano Maffei, Piaget Donfack Bouaka, Francesco Molinaro 4Science, Italy</p>	<p>Repository Showdown 1 Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Richard Jones, Cottage Labs Session Chair B: Heather Greer Klein, Samvera Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778589</p> <p>Fedora – The Open-Source Repository Platform Supporting Long-Term Digital Preservation Best Practices Arran Griffith Fedora</p> <p>Hyku Nic Don Stanton-Roark PALNI, United States of America</p> <p>Hyrax Nicholas Homenda Tufts University, United States of America</p>
15:00 - 15:50	<p>Presentations: AI & Software Preservation Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Paul Walk, Antleaf Ltd. Session Chair B: Iryna Kuchma, Electronic Information for Libraries (EIFL) Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778591</p> <p>Large Language Models for Software Mention Extraction David Pride¹, Matteo Guenci², Martin Dočekal³, Silvio Peroni², Petr Knoth¹ 1: CORE, KMI, The Open University, United Kingdom; 2: University of Bologna; 3: Brno University of Technology</p> <p>From Proof of Concept to Practice: A Repository for Preserving and Managing Running Applications Raman Ganguly University of Vienna, Austria</p>	<p>Repository Showdown 2 Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Heather Greer Klein, Samvera Session Chair B: Richard Jones, Cottage Labs Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778595</p> <p>Archipelago Commons: healthy and hearty soups (and pastries) from the community kitchen Diego Alberto Pino Navarro, Allison Sherrick Metropolitan New York Library Council, United States of America</p> <p>Repository Showdown: Dataverse Gustavo Durand Harvard University, United States of America</p> <p>Repository Showdown: Islandora Aubrey Shanahan Islandora Foundation, United States of America</p>
16:00 - 16:50	<p>Presentations: Trust Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Allison Sherrick, Metropolitan New York Library Council Session Chair B: Leila Sterman, Montana State University Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778597</p> <p>Advancing Trustworthy Repositories: The Role of Certification and Self-Assessment within the World Data System Community Daniela Santos Oliveira¹, David Castle², Dale Peters¹, Claudia Bauzer Medeiros³, Ioana Popescu⁴, Devika Madalli⁵, Rebecca Koskela¹, Meredith Goins¹, Suzie Allard⁶ 1: World Data System, United States of America; 2: University of Victoria, Victoria, BC, Canada; 3: Institute of Computing, University of Campinas, SP, Brazil; 4: ydroinformatics and Socio-technical Innovations, IHE Delft Institute for Water Education, Delft, The Netherlands; 5: INFLIBNET Centre, New Delhi, India; 6: University of Tennessee-Knoxville, United States of America</p> <p>Bringing Back Trust on the Internet: Authenticity, Content Credentials, and Digital Collections Quinn Sluzenski, Dan Zellner Northwestern University Libraries, United States of America</p>	<p>Repository Showdown 3 Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Erin Jerome, University of Massachusetts Amherst Session Chair B: Maureen Walsh, The Ohio State University Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778599</p> <p>DSpace Erik Moore University of Minnesota, United States of America</p> <p>EPrints3: Continuous Developer and Community Driven Repository Development in an Ever-changing Research Landscape Will Fyson, Rory McNicholl, Eleanor Dumbill CoSector, University of London, United Kingdom</p> <p>InvenioRDM repository showdown Nicola Tarocco¹, Alexandros Ioannidis¹, Sara Gonzales² 1: CERN, Switzerland; 2: Northwestern University, Galter Health Sciences Library & Learning Center, Chicago, IL, USA</p>
17:00 - 17:50	<p>Presentations: FAIR Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Kimberly Chapman, University of Arizona Libraries Session Chair B: Joseph Kraus, Colorado School of Mines Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778603</p> <p>Operationalizing FAIR in National Research Information Systems: The BrCris Example and Its Role in Open Repositories Washington Luís Ribeiro de Carvalho Segundo¹, Thiago Magela Dias², Marcel Garcia Souza¹, Fábio Lorensi do Canto³, Priscila Machado Sena¹ 1: Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (IBICT), Brazil; 2: Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG), Brazil; 3: Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC), Brazil</p>	<p>Presentations: DSpace Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Leila Sterman, Montana State University Session Chair B: Erin Jerome, University of Massachusetts Amherst Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778605</p> <p>We have liftoff! Launching DSpace 10.0, the first stage in the merger with DSpace-CRIS Tim Donohue, Holger Lenz LYRASIS, United States of America</p> <p>Non-English DSpace user interfaces: Common pitfalls and how to avoid them</p>

Connecting Global Agricultural Research: FAO AGRIS as a FAIR and Digital Public Good Infrastructure

Maidelyn Diaz Perez, Tiziano Di Condina, Alicia García García, Jaime García Llopis, Jose Hernández Meléndez, Tiziano Lorenzetti, Irena Mnatsakanyan, Mercy Moyo, Onan Mulumba, Chelsey Scalese, Imma Subirats-Coll
Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Italy

Ignace Deroost, Art Lowel, Lieven Droogmans

Atmire, Belgium

<p>11:00 - 11:50</p>	<p>Developer Track: DSpace 2 (Automated Metadata and Full Text Population) Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Iryna Kuchma, Electronic Information for Libraries (EIFL) Session Chair B: Erin Jerome, University of Massachusetts Amherst Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778607</p> <p>Fill The Gap – Automated retrieval of full text from emerging open APIs Cillian Joy¹, Bram Luyten² 1: University of Galway, Ireland; 2: Atmire</p> <p>Reducing Barriers: Automating Metadata Extraction in Submission Forms for DSpace Repositories José Carvalho, Carlos Silva, Paulo Lima, Henrique Malheiro, Pedro Pinto, Tiago Oliveira KEEP Solutions, Portugal</p>	<p>Presentations: Presenting Metadata Differently Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Ianthe Sutherland, University of Edinburgh Session Chair B: Richard William Fyson, CoSector, University of London Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778609</p> <p>Beyond FAIR: Designing Cognitive Accessibility in Data-Rich Repositories Aga Domanska Cottage Labs, United Kingdom</p> <p>Public Health Data in Context: Publishing the RKI research graph Luca Leopold¹, Franziska Diehr¹, Nicholas Drebenstedt¹, Richard Jones² 1: Robert Koch Institute, Germany; 2: Cottage Labs, United Kingdom</p>
<p>12:00 - 12:50</p>	<p>Panel: Connecting Research Assets: RAiD (Research Activity Identifier) and Repositories Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Isabel Bernal, CSIC (Spanish National Research Council) Session Chair B: Nick Sheppard, University of Leeds Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20789045</p> <p>Connecting Research Assets: RAiD (Research Activity Identifier) and Repositories Sheila Rabun¹, Matthias Liffers², Bryan Gee³, Trent Dunkin⁴, Sigrid Kelsey⁴ 1: Lyrasis, United States of America; 2: Australian Research Data Commons, Australia; 3: University of Texas at Austin, United States of America; 4: Louisiana State University, United States of America</p>	<p>Presentations: Openness & AI Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Leigh Stork, University of Strathclyde Session Chair B: Adrian Ho, American University of Sharjah Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778611</p> <p>When Openness Meets a Breaking Point: Perspectives on capacity, responsibility and stewardship under the threat of AI-driven harvesting. Arran Griffith¹, Allison Sherrick², Pino Navarro Diego Alberto² 1: Fedora; 2: Metropolitan New York Library Council</p> <p>Repository Practices for the Dark Arts: When Openness Conflicts with Safety Domhnall Carlin Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom</p>
<p>13:00 - 13:50</p>	<p>Developer Track: DSpace 3 (Performance and AI Enhancement) Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Iryna Kuchma, Electronic Information for Libraries (EIFL) Session Chair B: Ianthe Sutherland, University of Edinburgh Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778615</p> <p>DSpace Reimagined: AI-Powered Search and Accessibility Małgorzata Paszkowska, Maciej Iwaniszewski, Mateusz Adamiak PCG Academia, Poland</p> <p>Challenges and solutions for reliable and performant DSpace repositories Andrea Bollini, Giuseppe Digilio, Alexandru Raileanu 4Science, Italy</p>	<p>Presentations: Cultural Heritage Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Nick Sheppard, University of Leeds Session Chair B: William J. Nixon, Research Libraries UK (RLUK) Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778617</p> <p>Historica: Exploring Cultural Heritage Through Space and Time with DSpace-GLAM Martina Caroli², Marialaura Vignocchi², Campione Ludovica¹, Claudio Cortese¹, Benedetta Luisa Gandolini¹, Immacolata Scancarello¹ 1: 4Science, Italy; 2: ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - Università di Bologna, Italy</p> <p>Open to All? Repository Workflows for Ethical Access, FAIRness, and Cultural Heritage Data Sanjin Muftic, Thomas Slingsby University of Cape Town, South Africa</p>
<p>14:00 - 14:50</p>	<p>Panel: Repository Responses on the Frontline of the Artificial Intelligence Revolution Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Richard Jones, Cottage Labs Session Chair B: Leigh Stork, University of Strathclyde Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20789106</p> <p>Repository Responses on the Frontline of the Artificial Intelligence Revolution Maureen P. Walsh¹, Will Fyson², Steinn Sigurðsson³, Ianthe Sutherland⁴ 1: The Ohio State University, United States of America; 2: CoSector, University of London, United Kingdom; 3: arXiv, United States; 4: University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom</p>	<p>Presentations: National Repositories Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Emily Bongiovanni, Carnegie Mellon University Session Chair B: Nick Sheppard, University of Leeds Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778619</p> <p>Developing a national aggregator of open access repositories in Algeria: project proposal Ahcene Babori University of Tamanghasset, Algeria</p> <p>Reducing regional asymmetries in Brazil through digital repositories: the RBRD experience Priscila Sena¹, Dayane Dornelles², Phillipe Campos¹, Leticia Bonetti¹, Washington Carvalho-Segundo¹ 1: Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (Ibict), Brazil; 2: State University of Santa Catarina (UDESC); Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (Ibict), Brazil</p>
<p>15:00 - 15:50</p>	<p>Developer Track: DSpace 4 and Hyku (Upgrades and Customizations) Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Paul Walk, Antleaf Ltd. Session Chair B: William J. Nixon, Research Libraries UK (RLUK) Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778621</p> <p>Why harvest your own DSpace? Benefits of separating repository and search Ari Häyriäinen, Veli-Matti Häkkinen, Miika Nurminen, Toni Tourunen University of Jyväskylä, Finland</p> <p>Unpacking Hyku Knapsack: Sustainable Customization With Less Upgrade Pain Shana Moore</p>	<p>Presentations: Scaling Agile Practices & APTrust Roadmap Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Joseph Kraus, Colorado School of Mines Session Chair B: Erin Jerome, University of Massachusetts Amherst Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778623</p> <p>TigerData's Big Year: Scaling Agile Practices Across Diverse Teams to Support Research Activity Kate Lynch, Hector Correa Princeton University, United States of America</p> <p>New Horizons: How APTrust Developed a Community-Centered Technical Roadmap Process for Digital Preservation Melissa Iori</p>

16:00 - 16:50

Panel: Balancing Act: Achieving Accessible and Sustainable Repositories

Location: **Parallel Session 1**

Session Chair A: **Heather Greer Klein**, Samvera

Session Chair B: **Kimberly Chapman**, University of Arizona Libraries

Recording available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20789004>

Balancing Act: Achieving Accessible and Sustainable Repositories

Teresa Schultz¹, **Emily Boss**¹, **Leila Sterman**², **Rachel Molina**³

1: University of Nevada, Reno, United States of America; 2: Montana State University, United States of America; 3: Indiana University Indianapolis, United States of America

Presentations: Metadata Workflows & Service Design

Location: **Parallel Session 2**

Session Chair A: **Richard William Fyson**, CoSector, University of London

Session Chair B: **Allison Sherrick**, Metropolitan New York Library Council

Recording available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778625>

Open research information in repositories - modelling repository metadata workflows

Bárbara Rivera López¹, **Jermeja Grasic**², **Bianca Kramer**¹

1: Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information; 2: University of Maribor Library

Institutional repository service design at NYU Libraries

Laura Henze, **Jonathan Greenberg**, **Deb Verhoff**

New York University, United States of America

<p>12:00 - 12:50</p>	<p>Panel: When "Open to All" Threatens Sustainability: AI, Bots, and the Future of Open Repositories Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Ellen Ramsey, Big Ten Academic Alliance Session Chair B: Richard Jones, Cottage Labs Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20788969</p> <p>When "Open to All" Threatens Sustainability: AI, Bots, and the Future of Open Repositories Aaron McCollough¹, Tom Morrell², Mirek Simek³, Alex Ioannidis⁴ 1: Ubiquity Press, United States of America; 2: CalTech Library, United States of America; 3: CESNET, Czech Republic; 4: CERN, Switzerland</p>	<p>Presentations: Building Towards Interoperability & Shared Repository Service in Canada Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Adrian Ho, American University of Sharjah Session Chair B: Nick Sheppard, University of Leeds Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778628</p> <p>Building community towards interoperability: communities of practice, repositories, and universal indexing Priscilla Carmini¹, Emily Hopkins², Brianna Calomino³, Robyn Hall⁴, Tim Ribaric⁵, Amber Saundry⁶, Sophie St-Cyr⁷, Carolyn Sullivan⁸ 1: University of Waterloo, Canada; 2: University of Saskatchewan; 3: University of Calgary; 4: MacEwan University; 5: Brock University; 6: University of British Columbia; 7: Université de Sherbrooke; 8: Université d'Ottawa</p> <p>Shared Knowledge, Shared Progress: Building a Shared Repository Service with a Network of Experts Julia Gilmore¹, Gabriela Mircea² 1: University of Toronto, Canada; 2: University of Calgary, Canada</p>
<p>13:00 - 13:50</p>	<p>Developer Track: Dryad and Islandora (Features) Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Kate Blalack, University of Notre Dame Session Chair B: Iryna Kuchma, Electronic Information for Libraries (EIFL) Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778631</p> <p>Leveling Up a Repository Submission Process Ryan Scherle, Audrey Hamelers Dryad, United States of America</p> <p>Islandora Introduction: Core Features and Beyond Vlastimil Krejčíř, Ilyria Brejchová, Alžbeta Strakošová, Jan Adler Masaryk University, Czech Republic</p>	<p>Presentations: Including publishers in PIDs & arXiv Updates Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Maureen Walsh, The Ohio State University Session Chair B: Amanda French, Crossref Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778633</p> <p>Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): Are there still important PIDs missing? Investigation on agreements with publishers Julia Bartlewski¹, Robert Bosek², Christoph Broschinski¹, Gernot Deinzer², Cornelia Lang², Dirk Pieper¹, Bianca Schweighofer², Colin Sippel², Lisa-Marie Stein³, Alexander Wagner³, Silke Weiheit² 1: University of Bielefeld, Germany; 2: University of Regensburg, Germany; 3: Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY Hamburg, Germany</p> <p>Scaling for growth: Aligning people, policy, and infrastructure for a robust future Jim Entwood, Rebecca Rich Goldweber, Stephanie Orphan arXiv, United States of America</p>
<p>14:00 - 14:50</p>	<p>Developer track: OJS and DLMC (Preservation) Location: Parallel Session 2 Session Chair A: Amanda French, Crossref Session Chair B: Kate Blalack, University of Notre Dame Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778635</p> <p>Automating Digital Preservation in OJS: Integrating JATS XML, PDF/A, and BagIt for Seamless Repository Integration Santiago Soler^{1,2}, Tomas Nahuel Messineo^{1,2}, Santiago Fernández^{1,2}, Leonardo Luna^{1,2}, García Dolores^{3,4}, Gonzalo Lujan Villarreal^{1,2,3,4}, Ariel Lira^{1,2} 1: Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentine Republic; 2: PREBI-SEDICI; 3: Comisión de Investigaciones Científicas; 4: CESSI</p> <p>The DLMC Technology, The Swiss Army Knife of Digital Preservation: Research Data, Administrative/Heritage Data and Innovation Hugues CAZEAUX, Pierre-Yves BURGI University of Geneva, Switzerland</p>	<p>Presentations: OA Public Health Archive & Platform for OERs Location: Parallel Session 1 Session Chair A: Adrian Ho, American University of Sharjah Session Chair B: Joseph Kraus, Colorado School of Mines Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20778637</p> <p>Right To Know: How Legal Milestones Launched an Open Access Public Health Archive Kate Tasker, Emma James, Melissa Ignacio, Rachel Taketa University of California San Francisco, United States of America</p> <p>Building a lightweight national platform for OERs in international collaboration Jörg Pareigis¹, Anna Wolke², Axel Klinger³ 1: Karlstad University, Sweden; 2: Linnaeus University, Sweden; 3: TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, Germany</p>
<p>15:00 - 17:00</p>	<p>Wrap up & Closing Keynote Session Chair A: Elizabeth Krznarich, University of Wisconsin Session Chair B: Ianthe Sutherland, University of Edinburgh Recording available at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20789143</p> <p>Closing Keynote: From rescue to resilience: Strengthening open data infrastructures in times of crisis Kathleen Gregory Leiden University, Netherlands</p>	